

AIR POLLUTION PREDICTION USING AR AUTOREGRESSIVE MODEL

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Abstract:

- 1_ It became clear that there is an overlapping relationship between the elements (CO, SO₂, NO₂) for the variables under study.
- 2_ It became clear that over time the volume of air pollutants (CO, SO₂, NO₂) increases.
- 3_ It became clear that at least one sample out of four samples for one element meets the condition of a relationship.

Introduction:

Environmental pollution is one of the most important threats facing our planet in this era, and environmental pollution is a global issue, and is common in all countries.

Environmental pollution occurs when human activities introduce pollutants into the environment, which disrupts the vital routine processes in the environment, causing catastrophic changes in it, and the factors causing pollution are called pollutants, and pollutants are substances that occur in nature or are created due to intrusive human activities, and pollutants can also be forms of energies that are released into the environment, and pollution is considered one of the most controversial and interesting topics at all times and times by global citizens because of its catastrophic effects on everything on this earth.

Although there are a large number of people who care about the level of pollution that our earth faces, there are still many people who ignore this problem, and some people may continue to do some activities that produce more pollution to the environment, and environmental pollution may cause great harm to the ecosystem depends on the health of this environment, and air and water pollution can cause the death of

many living organisms in the ecosystem, including humans, and according to some reports, 14,000 people die every day in the world due to pollution, so a healthy environment is a prerequisite for a healthy life for us and our children, and fighting pollution is the best way to keep our environment healthy.

Objective:

The research aims to achieve a prediction of pollution levels for the elements under study, which are (NO₂, SO₂, CO).

Hypothesis:

H₀: (There is no significant relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables)

H₁: (There is a significant relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables)

Where:

The independent variables are (lag1, lag2, lag3) for each dependent variable and the dependent variables are (SO₂, NO₂, CO).

Environmental pollution:

It is the introduction of pollutants into the natural environment that causes a negative change. Pollution can take the form of chemicals or energy (such as noise, heat, or light) or air pollution. Pollution is often classified as point source pollution or non-point source pollution.

Types of environmental pollution and their causes:

1_ Air pollution:

It means mixing the air with certain materials, such as exhaust fuel and smoke. Air pollution can harm the health of plants and animals, and destroy buildings and other structures. The World Health Organization estimates that approximately one-fifth of the world's population is exposed to dangerous levels of air pollutants. The atmosphere, in its natural state, consists of nitrogen, oxygen, small amounts of carbon dioxide, other gases, and particulates (fine particles of liquid or solid materials).

A number of natural processes work to maintain the balance between the components of the atmosphere. For example, plants consume carbon dioxide and release oxygen, and animals in turn consume oxygen and produce carbon dioxide through the respiratory cycle. Gases and particulates are emitted into the atmosphere as a result of forest fires and volcanoes, where they are swept away or scattered by rain and wind.

Air pollution occurs when factories and vehicles release large amounts of gases and particulates into the air, making natural processes unable to maintain the balance of the atmosphere.

There are two main types of pollution:

Outdoor air pollution Hundreds of millions of tons of gases and particulates are released into the atmosphere each year.

Most of this pollution is caused by the burning of fuel used to power vehicles and heat buildings, but some pollution is also released by industrial and commercial processes. For example, ethylene perchloride (a dangerous pollutant) is used in many dry cleaning plants to remove dirt from clothes. Burning waste can release smoke and heavy metals such as lead and mercury into the atmosphere, and most heavy metals are very toxic.

One of the most common outdoor air pollutants is smog, a hazy, brown mixture of gases and particulates that forms when certain gases released by the burning of fuel and other petroleum products react with sunlight in the atmosphere. This reaction produces harmful chemicals that form smog.

One of the chemicals in smog is a toxic form of oxygen called ozone. Exposure to high concentrations of ozone causes headaches, burning eyes, and respiratory irritation in many people. In some cases, ozone in the lower layers of the atmosphere can be fatal. Ozone can also destroy plant life, even killing trees. Acid rain is the term given to rain and other forms of precipitation that are polluted mainly by sulfuric and nitric acids. These acids are formed when sulfur dioxide and nitrogen oxides react with water vapor in the air.

These gases are produced mainly by the burning of coal, gas, and oil in vehicles, factories, and power plants. The acids in acid rain move through the air and water, causing damage to the environment over vast areas.

Acid rain has killed entire fish populations in a number of lakes. It also damages buildings, bridges, and monuments.

Scientists believe that high concentrations of acid rain can damage forests and soil. Areas affected by acid rain include large parts of eastern North America, Scandinavia, and central Europe.

Chemical pollutants called chlorofluorocarbons and carbon dioxides deplete the ozone layer in the upper atmosphere. These compounds are used in refrigerators, air conditioners, and in the manufacture of plastic foam insulation.

Ozone, the harmful pollutant found in smog, forms a protective layer in the upper atmosphere, shielding the Earth's surface from more than 95% of the sun's ultraviolet radiation. Because chlorofluorocarbons and carbon dioxide reduce the ozone layer, more ultraviolet radiation reaches the Earth. Excessive exposure to these radiations destroys plants and increases people's risk of skin cancer.

The greenhouse effect is the heating caused by the atmosphere trapping the sun's heat. This phenomenon is caused by carbon dioxide, methane, and other atmospheric gases, which allow the sun's rays to reach the earth but prevent heat from escaping from the atmosphere. These gases that trap heat are called greenhouse gases.

The burning of fossil fuels and other human activities increase the amount of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. Many scientists believe that this increase intensifies the greenhouse effect and leads to a rise in global temperatures. This increase in temperature, called global warming, can cause many problems. The greenhouse effect, if strong, can cause glaciers and polar ice caps to melt and cause coastal flooding. It can also cause changes in rainfall patterns, which in turn leads to increased droughts and severe tropical storms.

Methods:

Autoregressive model (AR)

Autoregressive model (AR model for short) is a statistical method for processing time series. It is used to describe the relationship between current values and historical values. It uses historical time data of variables to predict themselves. The model must meet the requirements of centrality.

For example, the historical data of each time series of a time series data set X ranges from X_1 to X_{t-1} . Assuming that they have a linear relationship, the performance of X_t in the current period can be predicted. The current value of X is equal to a linear combination of one or more backward periods, plus a constant term and a random error.

Definition of the formula for an autoregressive process of order p :

$$X_t = c + \sum_{i=1}^p \varphi_i X_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

Field explanation:

X_t : is the performance of X in the current period

c: is a constant term.

p: is the order, i is the value from 1 to . p

Φ_i : is the autocorrelation coefficient.

t: is the time period.

ε_t : is the random error with mean 0 and standard deviation δ and ε is independent of t

For the first-order autoregressive model, it is represented by (1AR), and the simplified formula is:

$$X_t = c + \varphi X_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Autoregression is developed from linear regression analysis, but only the analysis of the independent variable x on the dependent variable y becomes the analysis of the independent variable x on itself.

Limitations of the autoregressive model:

Autoregressive models use their own data to make predictions, but this method is subject to certain limitations:

A- It must be constant, which requires that the random characteristics of the random process do not change over time.

B- It must have autocorrelation. If the autocorrelation coefficient (φ_i) is less than 0.5, it should not be used, otherwise the prediction result will be very inaccurate.

C- Autoregression is only suitable for predicting phenomena related to its own previous period, that is, phenomena that are greatly influenced by its own historical factors. For phenomena influenced by other factors, autoregression should not be used, and vector autoregressive models can be used instead.

Characteristics of stationary time series:

The constant requires that the random property of the random process that produces the time series Y does not change with time, and the process is said to be stationary; if the random property of the random process changes with time, the process is said to be non-stationary.

The constant is the fitting curve obtained from the sample time series, which can continue to follow the current pattern for a period of time in the future; if the data is non-stationary, it means that the shape of the

sample fitting curve does not have a continuous shape The characteristics, that is, the fitted curve will not conform to the shape of the current curve.

- The mean and variance of the random variable Y_t are independent of time. t
- The variance of the random variables Y_t and Y_s is only related to the time difference (step size). $t-s$
- For stationary time series, there are relatively rich mathematical processing methods, and non-stationary time series are converted into stationary time series processing by variation.

Table (1)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.033	.134		7.717	.001
	lag1	-.391	.149	-.654	-2.618	.047
	lag2	-.214	.119	-.440	-1.791	.133
	lag3	.017	.124	.034	.137	.896

a. Dependent Variable: CO

Andalusia Station 2015 for the element (CO)

The table above shows the standard and non-standard regression coefficients, the standard error, and the t-test value with the probability value of the tests (statistical significance). Since the value of (sig) for lag1 is less than 0.05, as it is the only variable that has significance in the regression equation, and thus we know which independent variable has an effect.

Table (2)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.062	.197		-.312	.768
	lag1	.357	.444	.315	.803	.458
	lag2	.669	.437	.506	1.531	.186
	lag3	.329	.840	.131	.391	.712

a. Dependent Variable: CO

Yarmouk Station 2015 for the element (CO)

The table above shows the standard and non-standard regression coefficients, the standard error, and the t-test value with the probability value of the tests (statistical significance). We note that the value of (sig) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, which indicates that there is no significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table (3)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.037	.301		-.123	.907
	Lag1	-.310	.418	-.309	-.742	.491
	Lag2	.575	.561	.514	1.025	.353
	Lag3	.730	.714	.537	1.022	.354

a. Dependent Variable: CO
Yarmouk station 2016 for the element (CO)

We notice that the value of (sig) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, which indicates that there is no significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table (4)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.714	.387		1.845	.124
	lag1	-.195	.432	-.197	-.452	.670
	lag2	-.204	.386	-.228	-.530	.619
	lag3	-.071	.385	-.081	-.185	.860

a. Dependent Variable: co
Andalusia Station 2016 for the element (CO)

We notice that the value of (sig) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, and this indicates that there is no significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table (5)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.059	.039		1.508	.192
	lag1	-.049	.440	-.050	-.112	.915
	lag2	-.153	.441	-.153	-.347	.743
	lag3	-.077	.440	-.078	-.175	.868

a) Dependent Variable: NO2
Yarmouk Station 2015 for the element (NO2)

We notice that the value of (sig) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, which indicates that there is no significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table (6)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.158	.111		1.420	.215
	lag1	.953	.733	.810	1.299	.251
	lag2	-.391	1.038	-.319	-.377	.722
	lag3	-.314	.741	-.251	-.424	.689

a. Dependent Variable: NO2
Yarmouk station 2016 for the element (NO2)

We notice that the value of (sig) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, which indicates that there is no significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table (7)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.023	.026		.862	.428
	lag1	.573	.421	.511	1.362	.231
	lag2	.167	.553	.113	.302	.775
	lag3	-.522	.636	-.288	-.820	.449

a. Dependent Variable: NO2
Andalusia Station 2015 for the element (NO2)

We notice that the value of (sig) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, and this indicates that there is no significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table (8)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.038	.011		3.292	.022
	lag1	.188	.268	.198	.702	.514
	lag2	.093	.175	.160	.531	.618
	lag3	-.369	.151	-.782	-2.437	.059

a. Dependent Variable: NO2
Andalusia Station 2016 for the element (NO2)

We notice that the value of (sig) is less than the significance level of 0.05, which indicates the existence of a significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table (9)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.016	.010		1.711	.148
	lag1	-.122	.439	-.122	-.278	.792
	lag2	-.271	.399	-.287	-.679	.527
	lag3	-.205	.412	-.217	-.497	.640

a. Dependent Variable: SO2
Yarmouk station 2015 for the element (SO2)

We notice that the value of (sig) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, which indicates that there is no significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table No. (10)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.016	.015		-1.045	.344
	lag1	.358	.338	.266	1.059	.338
	lag2	1.101	.386	.745	2.856	.036
	lag3	.015	.261	.015	.057	.957

a. Dependent Variable: SO2
Andalusia Station 2015 for the element (SO2)

Since the value of (sig) for lag2 is less than 0.05, as it is the only variable that has significance in the regression equation, and thus we know which independent variable has an effect.

Table (11)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.884	1.848		-1.019	.355
	lag1	.233	.421	.233	.554	.604
	lag2	-.453	.429	-.419	-1.057	.339
	lag3	64.203	53.532	.487	1.199	.284

a. Dependent Variable: SO2
Andalusia Station 2016 for the element (SO2)

We notice that the value of (sig) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, which indicates that there is no significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table (12)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.612	.193		3.167	.006
	lag1	-.016	.218	-.018	-.073	.943
	lag2	-.140	.200	-.169	-.697	.495
	lag3	.107	.200	.129	.534	.600

a. Dependent Variable: CO

Andalusia CO

We notice that the value of (sig) is less than the significance level of 0.05, which indicates the existence of a significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table (13)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.043	.012		3.538	.003
	lag1	.343	.236	.343	1.452	.165
	lag2	-.373	.235	-.373	-1.591	.130
	lag3	-.228	.237	-.228	-.965	.348

a. Dependent Variable: NO2

Andalusia NO2

We notice that the value of (sig) is less than the significance level of 0.05, which indicates the existence of a significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table (14)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.029	.029		.989	.336
	lag1	.873	.242	.871	3.604	.002
	lag2	-.030	.321	-.030	-.093	.927
	lag3	-.064	.243	-.063	-.263	.796

a. Dependent Variable: SO2

Yarmouk SO2

Since the value of (sig) for lag1 is less than 0.05, as it is the only variable that has significance in the regression equation, and thus we know which independent variable has an effect.

References:

1. Forecasting, Time Series, and Regression by Bruce L. Bowerman (Author), Richard O'Connell (Author), Anne Koehler (Author)
2. Regression Models for Time Series Analysis(by Benjamin kedem, konstantions fokianos
3. <https://ar.wikipedia.org/wiki/>
4. <https://mawdoo3.com/>
5. <https://almandab.com/>